

Emotional Intelligence and Work Values of Selected Instructors from a Teacher Education Institution

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Abstract: *This study aimed to assess the emotional intelligence and work values of the selected instructors from a teacher education institution. The researcher used a descriptive correlational design in this study with the questionnaire as the main instrument of gathering data. Thirty instructors took part in the survey via convenience sampling. For the instrument, an adapted and modified version of the Emotional Intelligence Self-Assessment Questionnaire (1998) and Work Values Inventory (2006) was used. The researcher subjected the data with the following tools: Weighted Mean, t-test, ANOVA and Pearson-r with the help of SPSS 20. This study generated the following results: instructors agree moderately on the different indicators of emotional intelligence. The instructors also stated that all the indicators are important for the work values inventory. There are no significant differences found in the emotional intelligence and work values when grouped according to sex, civil status, educational attainment, and length of service. However, in terms of age, the emotional intelligence got a significant difference. There is also no significant relationship found between the demographic profile, emotional intelligence, and work values of the instructors. Based on the results, the researcher endorsed relevant recommendations.*

Keywords— emotional intelligence, work values, faculty, teacher education institution

1. INTRODUCTION

Professionals run every institution and we consider a faculty employee as one. As Asio and Riego de Dios (2019) mentioned that educators are expected to have an impressive deal of professional and personal qualities and extraordinary skills. The personnel ensure the work and make stuffs happen. A set of motivated staff can turn work vision into a reality. In relation, Asio, Riego de Dios and Lapuz (2019) confirmed differences in the work ethics of professionals and relationship between professionalism and work ethics. Professional employees are the ones who gain knowledge of the institution and what it needs to run.

A group of motivated professionals equipped with the right set of values and emotional intelligence will most likely lead to a successful organizational venture. As Hubscher-Davidson (2019) discussed that emotional intelligence is a set of competencies showing the ability to recognize, understand and manage behaviors, moods and impulses. In addition, Petrides, Mikolajczak, Mavroveli, Sanchez-Ruiz, Furnham, and Pérez-González, (2016) also perceived trait emotional intelligence as perceptions of how well we believe we are in understanding, regulating, and expressing emotions to adapt to our environment and maintain well-being. If the employees are happy and content with themselves, this emanates into how they view the workplace beginning from the physical structure to the elements. Emotional intelligence is also the ability to perceive emotions, to use emotions to enhance thinking, to understand and label emotions, and regulate emotions in the self and other (Hubscher-Davidson, 2019). If the innate foundations of the employees are not functioning, this also shows in handling their coworkers and

the work itself. As van der Linden, Pekaar, Bakker, Schermer, Vernon, Dunkel, and Petrides, (2017) imposed that individuals with a high general factor of personality (GFP) score higher on trait and ability emotional intelligence, so the GFP is a social effectiveness factor. Zysberg, Orenshtein, Gimmon, and Robinson, (2017) stipulated that stress and emotional intelligence showed unique associations with burnout the values and the emotional intelligence of the workforce reflect the decisions they make and these affect the whole organization. As Rezvni, Chang, Wiewiora, Ashkanasy, Jordan and Zolin (2016) justified emotional intelligence as a positive impact on project success, job satisfaction and trust in an organization. Mérida-Lopez and Extremera (2017) pointed out in their review that there is a negative association between emotional intelligence and burnout dimensions.

With basic human values, work goals or work values are specific expressions of work values in the workplace. Without these specific perceptions, it will compromise work in the organization. In relation, Asio and Riego de Dios (2018) stipulated that the attributes could affect the skills of an individual. The original work goals are ranked by their importance as guiding principles for testing work outcomes and settings and for choosing among different work alternatives. Based on the study of Abessolo, Hirschi, and Rossier (2017), they suggested that a boundaryless-organizational mobility orientation has significant association with extrinsic/material work values. From the perspective of Visser, Gesthuizen, and Kraaykamp, (2019) showed that people who highly value extrinsic job rewards are even less politically active in individualist countries, whereas people who highly value intrinsic job aspects are more politically engaged. In addition, Gesthuizen,

Kovarek, and Rapp, (2019) clarified that there is a trade-off between the number of items researchers use to study work values and the number of countries analyzed if it aims for a more equivalent analysis of work values. In Jalalkamali, Ali, Hyun, and Nikbin (2016) work values were significantly related to relational communication satisfaction. This is another perspective that signifies the various importances of work values in the organization. However, in Ralston, Egri, Karam, Li and Fu (2018) they revealed the importance of delving beneath the national-level to gain a more fine-grained, regional-level understanding of values evolution. In another original point of view, Kalleberg, and Marsden (2019) exposed that there are some differences in work values are also because of aging or life course processes.

All persons involved in the organization should know how these factors affect the behavior of the employees in the workplace. This is to achieve better logistics, movement and delivery of goods and services. Cognizant of the foregoing, the researcher intends to undertake this study. Assessing the relationship between emotional intelligence and work values of the employees can provide valuable inputs. It can also help to enhance knowledge and handling techniques in teaching and in management.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational design with the survey questionnaire as the main instrument for gathering data. Since this study focused on describing the phenomena behind emotional intelligence and work values of instructors, the abovementioned design is applicable.

2.2 Respondents

There are 30 participants that took part in the data gathering. The researcher used a convenience sampling technique in choosing the participants since not all of the instructors were available during the survey. As for the basic criteria, the instructors were bona fide faculty, full-time in status and have been part of the institution for at least one year.

2.3 Instrument of the Study

In gathering the data, the researcher adapted and modified two sets of instruments the Work Values Inventory by Super (2006) and the Emotional Intelligence Self-Assessment Questionnaire by Goleman (1998). The researcher subjected it first to the reliability test before administering the actual data gathering. The reliability result is 0.96 in the alpha Cronbach test. The instrument has three parts: the demographic profile that differentiates the participants according to age, gender, civil status, educational experience and length of service in the company. Next is the part of the questionnaire that deals with the attribute of the employee’s emotional intelligences in terms of emotional awareness, managing their own emotions, self-

motivation, and empathy and coaching their own emotions. Last is the part of the questionnaire that describes the participants in terms of their work values in terms of achievement, challenge, independence, money, power, recognition, service to others and variety of tasks.

2.4 Statistical Analysis

The study used several statistical tools to compute like frequency and percentage for the profile variables, weighted mean for the emotional intelligence and work values, t-test and ANOVA for significant differences between the responses of the participants and Pearson-r for relationships among the variables. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20 computed the statistical analysis for the data. The researcher also used a Five point and Six point Likert scale for the weighted means of the study.

3. RESULTS

This study aimed to analyzes the emotional intelligence and work values of the selected instructors from a teacher education institution. It presents the following results:

Table 1. Profile of the Instructors

	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
21-30 years old	13	43
31-40 years old	10	33
41-50 years old	3	10
51 above	4	14
Gender		
Male	17	57
Female	13	43
Civil Status		
Single	22	73
Married	8	27
Educational Attainment		
BA/BS Graduate	6	19
MA/MS Units	20	67
MA/MS Graduate	4	14
Years in Service		
1-5 years	12	40
6-10 years	8	27
11-15 years	10	33
Total	30	100

Table 1 represents the demographic profile of the instructors. As seen, most of the instructors belong to the age bracket 21-30 years old, which means most of them are still young in the teaching field. There are more males than females, and the majority is still single. Most of the instructors are already studying their master’s degrees and are serving at least 1-5 years in the institution.

Table 2. Emotional Intelligence of the Instructors

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) Emotional Awareness	5.01	Agree Moderately
2) Managing One's Emotion	5.28	Agree Moderately
3) Self-Motivation	5.09	Agree Moderately
4) Empathy	5.05	Agree Moderately
5) Coaching Other's Emotion	4.98	Agree Moderately
Weighted Mean	5.08	Agree Moderately

* Legend: 5.50 – 6.00=Agree Very Much; 4.50 – 5.49=Agree Moderately; 3.50 – 4.49=Agree Slightly; 2.50 – 3.49=Disagree Slightly; 1.50 – 2.49=Disagree Moderately=1.00 – 1.49=Disagree Very Much

Table 2 shows the emotional intelligence of the instructors. As observed, indicator 2 got the highest mean with 5.28, which is equivalent to *agree moderately* on the Likert scale. Indicator 5 got the lowest mean with 4.98, with a descriptive interpretation of *agree moderately* on the Likert scale. The overall weighted mean is 5.08, and it has a Likert scale equivalent to *agree moderately*.

Table 3. Work Values of Instructors

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) Achievement	4.36	Important
2) Challenge	4.38	Important
3) Independence	4.30	Important
4) Money	4.20	Important
5) Power	4.21	Important
6) Recognition	4.29	Important
7) Service to Others	4.18	Important
8) Variety	4.25	Important
Weighted Mean	4.27	Important

* Legend: 4.50 - 5.00=Very Important; 3.50 – 4.49=Important; 2.50 – 3.49=Moderately Important; 1.50 – 2.49=Less Important; 1.00 – 1.49=Not Important

Table 3 shows the work values of the instructors. As perceived, indicator 2 got the highest mean with 4.38 with a Likert scale interpretation of *important*. Meanwhile, indicator 7 got the lowest mean score of 4.18, which is also has a Likert scale equivalence of *important*. The overall weighted mean is 4.27 and has a Likert scale equivalent to *important*.

Table 4a. T-test for Significant Differences in the Emotional Intelligence and Work Values of Instructors

	Male (n=17)		Female (n=13)		t- test
	M	SD	M	SD	
Emotional Intelligence	4.99	.50	5.07	.43	-0.51 (.61)
Work Values	4.23	.37	4.32	.37	-.64 (.53)

df = 28; p > .05

Table 4b. T-test for Significant Differences in the Emotional Intelligence and Work Values of Instructors

	Single (n=22)		Married (n=8)		t- test
	M	SD	M	SD	
Emotional Intelligence	5.07	.43	4.91	.58	0.82 (.42)
Work Values	4.22	.38	4.42	.31	-1.36 (.18)

df = 28; p > .05

Table 4a and 4b show the *t*-test for significant differences in emotional intelligence and work values of the instructors in terms of sex and civil status. Based on the results, there are no significant differences in the means of the instructors in terms of emotional intelligence and work values when grouped according to sex and civil status since emotional intelligence has *t* values of -0.51 (for sex) and 0.82 (for civil status) with corresponding *p* values of .61 and .42. The *p* values are higher than the designated alpha significance value of .05, thus, no substantial findings. Work values has *t* values of -.64 (for sex) and -1.36 (for civil status) with corresponding *p* values of .53 and .18 which are higher than the alpha significance level of .05, hence, no significant differences.

Table 5. ANOVA for Significant Differences in the Emotional Intelligence and Work Values of Instructors

		SS	dF	MS	F value
Emotional Intelligence (Age)	Between Groups	1.752	3	.584	3.339* (.035)
	Within	4.548	26	.175	
	Total	6.300	29		
Work Values (Age)	Between Groups	0.755	3	.252	2.081 (.127)
	Within	3.143	26	.121	
	Total	3.898	29		
Emotional Intelligence (Educ. Attain.)	Between Groups	0.510	2	.255	1.189 (.320)
	Within	5.790	27	.214	
	Total	6.30	29		

Work Values (Educ. Attain.)	Between Groups	0.118	2	.059	0.420 (.661)
	Within Total	3.780	27	.140	
Emotional Intelligence (Years in Service)	Between Groups	0.497	2	.249	1.157 (.329)
	Within Total	5.803	27	.215	
Work Values (Years in Service)	Between Groups	0.345	2	.172	1.311 (.286)
	Within Total	3.553	27	.132	
	Total	3.898	29		

* $p < .05$

Table 5 shows the analysis of variance for significant differences in the emotional intelligence and work values of instructors when grouped according to age, educational attainment and length of service. Emotional intelligence provided a significant result in terms of age since $F(3, 26) = 3.339, p = .035$, the result is lower than the alpha significance level of .05. However, in terms of work values, there is no significant finding since $F(3, 26) = 2.081, p = .127$ wherein the p value is higher than the alpha level of significance of .05. In terms of educational attainment, the results are unremarkable since the following results came out $F(2, 27) = 1.189, p = .320$ for emotional intelligence and $F(2, 27) = 0.420, p = .661$ for work values. The p values are higher than the alpha significance level of .05 thus, no significant differences in the result. For the years in service, it also yield no significant results since $F(2, 27) = 1.157, p = .329$ in the emotional intelligence and $F(2, 27) = 1.311, p = .286$ for work values. There p values were also higher than the alpha significance level of .05 hence, no significant differences from the result.

Table 6. Correlation Matrix between Demographic Profile, Emotional Intelligence and Work Values of Instructors

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Age	1						
Sex	-.009 (.964)	1					
Civil Status	.258 (.168)	.233 (.215)	1				
Educ. Attain.	.049 (.798)	.219 (.245)	.070 (.713)	1			
Length of Service	.601* (.000)	-.168 (.375)	.400* (.028)	-.009 (.962)	1		
Work Values	.143 (.452)	.119 (.530)	.249 (.185)	.075 (.694)	.199 (.291)	1	
Emotional Intelligence	-.145 (.446)	.096 (.614)	-.154 (.418)	.252 (.180)	-.156 (.409)	.216 (.252)	1

* $p > .05$

Table 6 exhibits the correlation matrix between demographic profiles, emotional intelligence and work values of the instructors. We can see that no relationship

exists between the three variables. This is because their p values are higher than the alpha significance value of .05. This only means that work values have no relationship to demographic profiles, so does the emotional intelligence. The work values also had no relationship to the emotional intelligence of the instructors in the study.

4. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to analyzing the emotional intelligence and work values of selected instructors from a teacher education institution and if there is any possibility of relationship between the two variables. The result is essential in many aspects of human resource management and in the organizational behavior itself. The results provided a substantial finding to some extent and areas on which human resource practitioners can benefit.

For the emotional intelligence results, it has a uniform finding with all of the responses falling into the context of agreeing moderately, this is so since in teaching profession, the environment is always changing. As Rao and Lakshmi (2018) stated that teachers undergoes stress because of the changes in the educational policies, globalization liberalization, and advances in the information technology. However, Petrides et al., (2016) stipulated that individual differences in trait emotional intelligences are a consistent predictor of human behavior across the life span. In addition, Supriyanto, Ekowati and Masyhuri (2019) showed that emotional intelligence could increase employee performance through organizational citizenship behavior. Di Fabio and Kenny (2016) also explored and explained the relationship of trait models of emotional intelligence for both pleasure and happiness of an individual. This is important in the organization for having employees with such traits in the workplace can influence others.

For the part of the work values, the instructors stated that all of the indicators were important. This only shows that the instructors have high work values in different terms. In the study of Politi-Salame, Obregón-Schael, Puga-Méndez, Stanley and Arciniega (2019), they found out that those who rate power as a relatively important value are more likely to violate professional conduct rules notwithstanding receiving training regarding ethical principles. Cemalcilar, Secinti, and Sumer (2018) showed that both mothers' and fathers' work values, and their parenting behavior were significantly associated with their children's work values. In a different note, Winter and Jackson (2016) stipulated that there are areas of work supportive of an efficient Generation Y performance relationship, and incompetent areas of performance where administrators and Generation Y hold diverse work values inclinations.

Statistical analysis provided a vivid result for this study. In terms of sex and civil status, there are no significant findings for both emotional intelligence and work values.

For educational attainment and length of service, we observed the same result. However, in terms of age, there is a significant finding for emotional intelligence but not with work values. In contrast, according to the study of Huo and Boxall (2018), they showed that work instrumentalism reduces the positive effect of training on job satisfaction while boosting the positive effect of remuneration on job satisfaction. Furnham and MacRae (2018) stated that males and younger people rated Recognition and Security as work motivational factors. In relation, Cabello, Sorrel, Fernández-Pinto, Extremera, and Fernández-Berrocal, (2016) showed that gender affects the total ability emotional intelligence score. However, Lukes, Feldman, and Vegetti, (2019) indicated that values related to self-employment are not rooted in a general value of work.

There is no significant relationship observed in this study between the demographic profile, emotional intelligence and work values. Yet a study by Kalleberg and Marsden (2019) indicated that work values are attributable to aging or life course processes, especially the greater importance placed on high income during the mid-life years. Additionally, Borg, Hertel, Krumm and Bilsky (2019), showed that work values is related to gender, educational level, and age of the respondents. Although not related, in the study of Miao, Humphrey and Qian (2017) found certain relationship between emotional intelligence with job satisfaction. Moreover, Lee and Chelladurai (2018) implied that emotional intelligence was significantly associated with all three forms of emotional labor in different directions.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the aforementioned results, the researcher therefore concluded that: the instructors *agree moderately* on the different indicators of the emotional intelligence. The instructors also stated that all the mentioned indicators for work values are *important*. There is no significant difference found in the emotional intelligence and work values when the instructors were grouped according to sex, civil status, educational attainment, and length of service. However, in terms of age, emotional intelligence got a substantial result but not with the work values. There is also no significant relationship found between the demographic profile, emotional intelligence and work values of the instructors.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are presented based on the results of the study:

- 1) The institution should set a self-awareness program for the faculty employees to create a better emotional foundation in their personality.
- 2) Constant checks on the reward system of the school for a better work output and a better working atmosphere for both the employer and the employee.
- 3) Occasional seminars and trainings for personality development and work values upliftment.

- 4) Annual psychological/ personality check-ups for faculty employee to enhance self-awareness and improve self-confidence and coping mechanisms.
- 5) Conduct a special program for faculty enhancement like InSET.
- 6) Annual auditing and evaluation of workloads of faculty members to see if the required number of hours of work affects their performance.

7. REFERENCES

- 1) Asio, J.M.R., & Riego de Dios, E.E. (2019). The college students' perspective on what makes an educator well-qualified. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 3 (3),126-138. <http://dx.doi.org/10.33902/jpr.v3i3.124>
- 2) Asio, J.M.R., & Riego de Dios, E.E. (2018). 21st century attributes and skills of a teacher in the perspective of college students. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED594675>
- 3) Asio, J.M.R., Riego de Dios, E.E., & Lapuz, A.M.E. (2019). Professional skills and work ethics of selected faculty in a local college. *PAFTE Research Journal*, 9 (1), 164-180. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3452971>
- 4) Abessolo. M., Hirschi. A. & Rossier. J. (2017). Work values underlying protean and boundaryless career orientations. *Career Development International*. 22(3), 241-259. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-10-2016-0167>
- 5) Borg. I., Hertel. G., Krumm. S., & Bilskv. W. (2019) Work values and facet theory: from intercorrelations to individuals. *International Studies of Management & Organization*, 49(3), 283-302. doi: [10.1080/00208825.2019.1623980](https://doi.org/10.1080/00208825.2019.1623980)
- 6) Cabello, R., Sorrel, M. A., Fernández-Pinto, I., Extremera, N., & Fernández-Berrocal, P. (2016). Age and gender differences in ability emotional intelligence in adults: A cross-sectional study. *Developmental Psychology*, 52(9),1486–1492. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000191>
- 7) Cemalcilar, Z., Secinti, E., & Sumer, N. (2018). Intergenerational transmission of work values: a meta-analytic review. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 47 (8), 1559–1579.
- 8) Di Fabio, A. & Kenny, M.E. (2016). Promoting well-being: The contribution of emotional intelligence. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 1182. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01182>
- 9) Furnham, A. & MacRae, I. (2018). The dark side of work values. *Current Psychology*, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-018-9873-z>
- 10) Gesthuizen. M., Kovarek. D., & Rann. C. (2019). Extrinsic and intrinsic work values: Findings on equivalence in different cultural contexts. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 682(1),60–83. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716219829016>

- 11) Hubscher-Davidson, S. (2019). Emotional intelligence and professional translation. In: CIOL AGM & Members' Day 2019, 16 Mar 2019, London, CIOI.
- 12) Huo, M. & Boxall, P. (2018). "Instrumental work values and responses to HR practices: A study of job satisfaction in a Chinese manufacturer", *Personnel Review*, 47 (1), 60-73.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-01-2017-0015>
- 13) Jalalkamali, M., Ali, A., Hvan, S. and Nikbin, D. (2016). Relationships between work values, communication satisfaction, and employee job performance: The case of international joint ventures in Iran. *Management Decision*, 54 (4), 796-814.
- 14) Lee, Y.H., & Chelladurai P. (2018). Emotional intelligence, emotional labor, coach burnout, job satisfaction, and turnover intention in sport leadership. *European Sport Management Quarterly*, 18(4), 393-412.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/16184742.2017.1406971>
- 15) Lukeš, M., Feldmann, M., & Vegetti, F. (2019). Work values and the value of work: different implications for young adults' self-employment in Europe. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 682 (1), 156–171.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716219828976>
- 16) Mérida-López, S., & Extremera, N. (2017). Emotional intelligence and teacher burnout: A systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 85, 121-130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2017.07.006>
- 17) Miao, C., Humphrey, R.H., & Qian, S. (2017). A meta-analysis of emotional intelligence and work attitudes. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 90 (2), 177-202.
- 18) Petrides, K. V., Mikolaiczak, M., Mavroveli, S., Sanchez-Ruiz, M.-J., Furnham, A., & Pérez-González, J.-C. (2016). Developments in trait emotional intelligence research. *Emotion Review*, 8(4), 335–341. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073916650493>
- 19) Politi-Salame, I., Obregón-Schael, D., Puga-Méndez, D., Stanley, L., & Arciniega, L. (2019). The relationship between individual work values and unethical decision-making and behavior at work. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 158 (4), 1133-1148.
- 20) Ralston, D.A., Egri, C.P., Karam, C.M., Li, Y., & Fu, P.P. (2018). Changes in work values across the regions of China. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 35 (1), 145–179.
- 21) Rao, R.V., & Lakshmi, G.B. (2018). Emotional intelligence of school teachers. *International Journal of Advance Research, Ideas and Innovations in Technology*, 4 (3), 2123-2125.
- 22) Rezvani, A., Chang, A., Wiewiora, A., Ashkanasy, N.M., Jordan, P.J., & Zolina, R. (2016). Manager emotional intelligence and project success: The mediating role of job satisfaction and trust. *International Journal of Project Management*, 34 (7), 1112-1122.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2016.05.012>
- 23) Supriyanto, A.S., Ekowati, V.M., & Masyhuri (2019). The relationship among spiritual intelligence, emotional intelligence, organizational citizenship behavior, and employee performance. *Etikonomi*, 18 (2), 249-258.
- 24) van der Linden, D., Pekaar, K. A., Bakker, A. B., Schermer, J. A., Vernon, P. A., Dunkel, C. S., & Petrides, K. V. (2017). Overlap between the general factor of personality and emotional intelligence: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 143(1), 36–52. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000078>
- 25) Visser, M., Gesthuizen, M., & Kraavkamp, G. (2019). Work values and political participation: a cross-national analysis. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 682 (1), 186–203. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716219830961>
- 26) Winter, R.P., & Jackson, B.A. (2016). Work values preferences of Generation Y: performance relationship insights in the Australian Public Service. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(17), 1997-2015.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1102161>
- 27) Zysberg, L., Orenshtein, C., Gimmon, E., & Robinson, R. (2017). Emotional intelligence, personality, stress, and burnout among educators. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 24(1), 122–136. <https://doi.org/10.1037/str0000028>